

Assess the Perceived Stress and Coping Strategies among GNM Student of Selected College of Nursing Bhubaneswar during Covid -19 Pandemic Lockdown

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ABSTRACT

Abstract: Objectives: To determine the stress level and coping level among GNM students of all batches in regard to covid 19 lockdown. To find out the association between stress level with their selected socio- demographic variable. To find out the association between coping level by the GNM student with their selected socio-demographic variable. Method: this is a cross sectional Quantitative study design; non experimental survey research approach was used. Data collected by means online questioners which is consisting of three sections-socio-demographic data tool, perceived stress scale, Brief coping scale. Result: In the study majority that is 70% of students were 21-25 years old and only 1% were 20 and above and 29% were between 17-20 years, for years of education majority were that is 63% were from 1st year, 24% were from 2nd year and 13% were 3rd year students. Sample were predominantly dominated by Hindu religion which was 92%, 6% were Christian and 2% were Muslim. 77% were hostellers, 14% were residing with family, 4% were with relatives and 5% were residing other. For basic qualification 99% had higher secondary education, 1% were graduate. And 99% were belongs to nuclear family, 10% were belongs to joint family. In parents occupation 83% were pvt. Employee, 13% were govt. employee, 2% were self-employee and 2% were unemployed. Samples 88% had no any co- morbidity condition and 12% present had co-morbidity condition. Most of the students had source of information for covid-19 from internet, 23% from television, 4% from peers, and 2% from other sources. Residing presently was significantly associated with the stress level of the student with p value 0.038, type of family significantly associated with stress level with p value 0.013, and co-morbidity significantly associated with stress level with p value 0.000. Religion was significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.006, Residing present significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.011, Type of family significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.001, co-morbidity was significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.000.

Conclusion: The findings of the study revealed that residing presently; type of family, co-morbidity has a significant association with stress level. Religion, residing presently, type of family, co-morbidity has a significant association with coping level. I have found that 12% were high stress score and majority 80% had moderate stress and 17% had low coping, 8% had high coping score. So it is crucial to give psychological support to all nursing students to overcome the stress in this pandemic.

KEYWORDS: Stress, Coping, GNM students, Covid 19 lockdown.

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INTRODUCTION

There were numbers of outbreaks which are pandemic epidemic has been seen from prehistoric time which been recorded.(1) The covid pandemic is one of the most contagious and life threatening kind of disease condition.(2)(13) This covid -19 left humankind in an uncertainty of future, still there was a hope for the life.(3) During this outbreak in the country and in our state, where people to get admitted in the hospital because of fear of the contagious covid-19, Nursing students are exposed to additional stress factors such as fear of being infected.(4) In 2013 during SARS outbreak in a study found that nursing students perceived themselves to be at higher risk of infection.(4)

Stress is tension, strain or pressure from a situation that requires us to use, adapt, or develop new coping skills.(5) Stress is a process of adjusting to or dealing with circumstances that disrupts or threaten to disrupt a person's physical or psychological functioning. Stressors can be internal or external, that will precipitate a change.(6) These stressors are the precipitating factors to make any change. Here in this corona pandemic this affects public life. In this, stresses that can affect the nursing students are the risk of having infected and study related stress.(7)

During the corona pandemic many people affected in numerous way, some get affected physically and some mentally.(8) This left people in numerous uncertainties such as loosing job, financial loss, loss of shelter, emotional isolation, inadequate resource for medical response, fear of

losing the loved one etc. Because of this types of uncertainty made them experience lots of emotional disturbances like Stress, insomnia, frustration, irritability which could leads to psychiatric disorders. (9)(10)

Covid-19 is a highly contagious infectious disease caused by a virus named corona virus which is belongs to group corona virus family.(10) COVID-19 was originated from china in the Wuhan city in 2019. All over the world huge number of affected cases and death has been found.(11) (13)

METHODOLOGY

This is a cross sectional Quantitative study design; non experimental survey research approach was used. purposive sampling techniques was used to select sample and the data was collected by means of online questioners which is consisting of three sections-socio-demographic data tool, perceived stress scale, Brief coping scale. Consent form the participants were obtained. The participant those were unwilling to complete the questionnaire due to personal reason were free to withdraw from the study. Data collection was done for 100 participants on in the second week of May.

Study variables

Age has been classified into three variables. Year of education has been categorized into three groups' 1st year 2nd year and 3rd year. Occupation of the parents has been classified in to four variables. Religion has been classified as Hindu, Christian, and Muslim. Co-morbidity condition are taken as present or absent because of this pandemic. And the source of information has been classified into four variables.

RESULTS

Table 1. Sample profile of the population

N=100

Criteria	Parameters	No of cases	Percentage (100)
Age (year)	17-20	29	29%
	21-25	70	70%
	26 & above	1	1%
Gender	Male	5	5%
	Female	95	95%
Year of education	1 st year	63	63%
	2 nd year	24	24%
	3 rd year	13	13%
Religion	Christian	6	6%
	Hindu	92	92%
	Muslim	2	2%
Residing presently	Hostel	77	77%
	With family	14	14%
	With relatives	4	4%

Assess the Perceived Stress and Coping Strategies Among GNM Student of Selected College of Nursing Bhubaneswar During Covid -19 Pandemic Lockdown

	Others	5	5%
Basic qualification	Higher secondary	99	99%
	Graduate	1	1%
Type of family	Joint	10	10%
	Nuclear	90	90%
Parents occupation	Govt. employee	13	13%
	Pvt. Employee	83	83%
	Self employee	2	2%
	Unemployed	2	2%
Co-morbidity	Present	12	12%
	Absent	88	88%
Source of information for COVID 19	Internet	71	71%
	Television	23	23%
	Peers	4	4%
	Others	2	2%

Table 1, reveals the sample population in numbers and percentage, majority that is 70% of students were 21-25 years old and only 1% were 20 and above and 29% were between 17-20 years. For years of education majority were that is 63% were from 1st year, 24% were from 2nd year and 13% were 3rd year students. Sample were predominantly dominated by Hindu religion which was 92%, 6% were Christian and 2% were Muslim. 77% were hostellers, 14% were residing with family, 4% were with relatives and 5% were residing other.

For basic qualification 99% had higher secondary education, 1% were graduate. 99% were belongs to nuclear family, 10% were belongs to joint family. In parent’s occupation 83% were Pvt. Employee, 13% were govt. employee, 2% were self employee and 2% were unemployed. Samples 88% had no co- morbidity condition and 12% had co-morbidity condition. Most of the students had source of information for covid-19 from internet, 23% from television, 4% from peers, and 2% from other sources.

Stress level

Table 2. Factors that affecting stress among nursing students.

Stress level of GNM students		High stress	Low stress	Moderate stress	Chi-sq	P- value
Gender	Male	1(8.3%)	0(0.0%)	4(5.0%)	0.702	0.784
	Female	11(91.7%)	8(100.0%)	76(95.0%)		
Year of education	1 st year	4(33.3%)	5(62.5%)	54(67.5%)	5.269	0.261
	2 nd year	5(41.7%)	2(25%)	17(21.2%)		
	3 rd year	3(25.0%)	1(12.5%)	9(11.2%)		
Religion	Christian	1(8.3%)	2(25.0%)	3(3.8%)	8.816	0.066
	Hindu	10(83.3%)	6(75.0%)	76(95.0%)		
	Muslim	1(8.3%)	0(0.0%)	1(1.2%)		
Residing presently	Hostel	5(41.7%)	6(75.0%)	66(82.5%)	13.324	0.038
	With family	4(33.3%)	2(25.0%)	8(10.0%)		
	With relatives	2(16.7%)	0(0.0%)	2(2.5%)		

Assess the Perceived Stress and Coping Strategies Among GNM Student of Selected College of Nursing Bhubaneswar During Covid -19 Pandemic Lockdown

	Others	1(8.3%)	0(0.0%)	4(5.0%)		
Basic qualification	Higher secondary	12(100.0%)	8(100.0%)	79(98.8%)	0.253	0.881
	Graduate	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	1(1.2%)		
Type of family	Joint	4(33.3%)	0(0.0%)	6(7.5%)	8.704	0.013
	Nuclear	8(66.7%)	8(100.0%)	74(92.5%)		
Parents occupation	Govt. employee	1(8.3%)	1(12.5%)	11(13.8%)	1.395	0.966
	Pvt. Employee	11(91.7%)	7(87.5%)	65(81.2%)		
	Self employee	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(2.5%)		
	Unemployed	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(2.5%)		
Co-morbidity	Absent	0(0.0%)	8(100.0%)	80(100.0%)	100.00	0.000
	Present	12(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)		
Source of information for COVID 19	Internet	9(75.0%)	7(87.5%)	55(68.8%)	5.766	0.450
	Peers	1(8.3%)	1(12.5%)	2(2.5%)		
	TV	2(16.7%)	0(0.0%)	21(26.2%)		
	Others	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(2.5%)		

Table -2 explains the factors such as gender, year of education, religion, residing presently, basic qualification, type of family, parents occupation, co-morbidity, source of information for covid-19 were analyzed for significance. Residing presently was significantly associated with the **Coping level**

stress level of the student with p value 0.038, type of family significantly associated with stress level with p value 0.013, and co-morbidity significantly associated with stress level with p value 0.000.

Table 3. Factors associated with coping strategies.

Coping level of GNM students		High Coping	Low Coping	Moderate Coping	Chi-sq	P- value
Gender	Male	0(0.0%)	2(11.8%)	3(4.0%)	2.217	0.330
	Female	8(100.0%)	15(88.2%)	72(96.0%)		
Year of education	1 st year	5(62.5%)	9(52.9%)	49(65.3%)	1.495	0.828
	2 nd year	2(25.0%)	6(35.3%)	16(21.3%)		
	3 rd year	1(12.5%)	2(11.8%)	10(13.3%)		
Religion	Hindu	6(75.0%)	14(82.4%)	72(96.0%)	9.305	0.006
	Muslim	0(0.0%)	1(5.9%)	1(1.3%)		
	Christian	2(25.0%)	2(11.8%)	2(2.7%)		
Residing presently	Hostel	6(75.0%)	8(47.1%)	63(84.0%)	16.525	0.011
	With family	2(25.0%)	4(23.5%)	8(10.7%)		
	With relatives	0(0.0%)	3(17.6%)	1(1.3%)		
	Others	0(0.0%)	2(11.8%)	3(4.0%)		
Basic qualification	Higher secondary	8(100.0%)	17(100.0%)	74(98.7%)	0.337	0.845
	Graduate	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	1(1.3%)		
Type of family	Joint	0(0.0%)	6(35.3%)	4(5.3%)	14.789	0.001
	Nuclear	8(100.0%)	11(64.7%)	71(94.7%)		

Assess the Perceived Stress and Coping Strategies Among GNM Student of Selected College of Nursing Bhubaneswar During Covid -19 Pandemic Lockdown

Parents occupation	Govt. employee	1(12.5%)	1(5.9%)	11(14.7%)	3.200	0.783
	Pvt. Employee	7(87.5%)	15(88.2%)	61(81.3%)		
	Self employee	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(2.7%)		
	Unemployed	0(0.0%)	1(5.9%)	1(1.3%)		
Co-morbidity	Absent	8(100.0%)	6(35.3%)	74(98.7%)	53.892	0.000
	Present	0(0.0%)	11(64.7%)	1(1.3%)		
Source of information for COVID 19	Internet	7(87.5%)	12(70.6%)	52(69.3%)	8.834	0.183
	Peers	1(12.5%)	2(11.8%)	1(1.3%)		
	TV	0(0.0%)	3(17.6%)	20(26.7%)		
	Others	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(2.7%)		

Table -3 explains the factors gender, year of education, religion, residing presently, basic qualification, type of family, parents occupation, co-morbidity, source of information for covid-19 were analyzed for significance. Religion was significantly associated with coping level with

p value 0.006, Residing present significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.011, Type of family significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.001, co-morbidity was significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.000.

Table 4. Stress score of the students

Stress score	No. of students	Percentage
0-13 (low)	8	8%
14-26 (moderate)	80	80%
27-40 (high)	12	12%

Table - 4 reveals the stress score of the student majority 80% had moderate stress score, 12% were high stress score and 8% were low stress score.

Coping score of the students

Figure 1. Shows Coping Score of GNM Students were, 75% had moderate coping, 17% had low coping, 8% had high coping.

DISCUSSION

In the study majority that is 70% of students were 21-25 years old and only 1% were 20 and above and 29% were between 17-20 years. For years of education majority were that is 63% were from 1st year, 24% were from 2nd year and 13% were 3rd year students. Sample were predominantly dominated by Hindu religion which was 92%, 6% were

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Assess the Perceived Stress and Coping Strategies Among GNM Student of Selected College of Nursing Bhubaneswar During Covid -19 Pandemic Lockdown

from television, 4% from peers, and 2% from other sources. Stress level: On Table -2 the present study explains the factors such as gender, year of education, religion, residing presently, basic qualification, type of family, parents occupation, co-morbidity, source of information for covid-19 were analyzed for significance. Residing presently was significantly associated with the stress level of the student with p value 0.038, type of family significantly associated with stress level with p value 0.013, and co-morbidity significantly associated with stress level with p value 0.000. Coping level: In Table -3 explains the factors gender, year of education, religion, residing presently, basic qualification, type of family, parents occupation, co-morbidity, source of information for covid-19 were analyzed for significance. Religion was significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.006, Residing present significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.011, Type of family significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.001, co-morbidity was significantly associated with coping level with p value 0.000. The present study reveals that in Stress score of the student majority 80% had moderate stress score, 12% were high stress score and 8% were low stress score. Coping Score 75% had moderate coping, 17% were low coping, 8% had high coping.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study revealed that residing presently; type of family, co-morbidity has a significant association with stress level. Religion residing presently, type of family, co-morbidity has a significant association with coping level. I have found that 12% were high stress score and majority 80% had moderate stress and 17% had low coping, 8% had high coping score. It is crucial to give psychological support to all nursing students to overcome the stress in this pandemic.

Ethical Permissions: Taken from the institutional ethics committee, SUM Nursing College, SOA University, Bhubaneswar.

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